

Drifting Ears on Rivers: A Scalable IoT-Based System for Spatiotemporal Mapping of Anthropogenic Noise Pollution in Freshwater Ecosystems

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Abstract:

Human activities have introduced widespread noise pollution into river ecosystems. Understanding this acoustic pollution is critical to quantify ecological impacts, identify dominant sources, and guide regulatory interventions. However, its spatial variability and ecological impacts remain poorly understood due to limited monitoring methods. To address this, we developed a low-cost, floating acoustic sensor system using Raspberry Pi Pico microcontrollers, GPS modules, IoT transmitters, and omnidirectional microphones, powered by AA batteries and enclosed in buoyant plastic shells. These devices were freely deployed along rivers to collect ambient sound data at high spatiotemporal resolution (1-minute intervals over ~200 km), enabling detailed noise mapping across diverse shoreline environments.

To analyze the acoustic data, we developed an integrated workflow that spatiotemporally pairs the drifter measurements with Automatic Identification System (AIS) ship trajectory data. We then implemented a Graph Convolutional Network (GCN) to model and predict underwater noise levels. The GCN uses key vessel features—including length, speed, distance, and direction—as input to capture complex, vessel-induced spatio-temporal noise patterns. The model demonstrates strong predictive capability, achieving a coefficient of determination of 0.592.

This pre-trained model enables the generation of high-resolution (10 m) noise distribution maps, revealing that ship traffic is the primary driver of the river's soundscape, accounting for 60% of total noise exposure. Our findings show that while the overall noise level along the 180-km river corridor was relatively homogeneous (60–100 dBA), our mapping successfully identified localized hotspots of intense noise (>100 dBA) that directly correspond to concentrated vessel activity zones. This integrated approach provides a robust and scalable framework for large-scale aquatic noise assessment, offering critical data for ecological management.

Key words: Anthropogenic Noise, River, Automatic Identification System, Graph Convolutional Network